

The Community Church of Apostles Nigeria and Oversea (COCANO), Ajegunle

By Adegbola Tolu Adefi, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

Entry tags: Christianity, Religious Group, Language, Aladura, Yoruba Language

In 1933, the Community Church of Apostles Nigeria and Oversea (COCANO) separated from the rapidly growing Aladura movement, a stock of the Cherubim and Seraphim Society introduced to Ilajeland in 1929. The members of the C & S movement in Ilajeland during this period were highly mobile holding their conventions across the towns and villages in Ilajeland. In 1933, they had attended a convention in Ereke. While most members returned to their communities, a group stayed back at the convention venue, making it their home with the intention of continuing there permanently. The group continued there until a time when the establishment of theocratic communities in Ilajeland gained currency. At this time, they decided to move to the natal town of the group's premier leader where enough provision had been made to accommodate them. Their relocation to Ajegunle follows the pattern of Wilson Eran Ikudehinbu who left Ayetoro for former Maran Apostles now Ori-Oke Iwamimo and Lot Korollo who also led his group from his former church location to merge his Christian group with his natal community of Oropo about two miles west of Mahin. At Ajegunle, the COCANO has continued to advance their beliefs as its spiritual fervour has had significant impact on the local community. The church holds its conventions, anniversaries and other special programmes in the community boosting local trade and businesses. It advances the global picture of Ajegunle and has continued to place the town on the public stage as the host community of the Christian group. The church has had its fair share of the succession debacle which has plagued most of the theocratic communities in Ilajeland but has found a way to overcome the challenges posed by this widespread problem. As with most of the other theocratic communities in Ilajeland, COCANO is organised along several bands for easy coordination and administration. The church appoints leaders for each band. The band leadership is responsible to the Oba (monarch) and the church council for the activities of the group and welfare of her members. Roles are assigned to various bands by the monarch towards the furtherance of the church programmes and agenda. Though there are subtle difference between the COCANO and some other theocratic communities in the area, the group still relates freely with these sister religious settlements within the region. They both offer and receive special invitations to participate in programmes and events marking important milestones in the life and history of one another.

Date Range: 1933 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ajegunle

Region tags: Western Africa, Nigeria, Africa

Ajegunle, Ilaje Local Government Area, Ondo State,
Nigeria

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/100070994161547/videos/872832154245682>

– Source 1 Description: A thanksgiving service characterised by singing and giving of offertory gifts

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.stepbible.org/version.jsp?version=YorBMYO>

– Source 1 Description: Yoruba bible

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/100070994161547/videos/718234449639067>

– Source 1 Description: A typical religious meeting of the COCANO group. Sourced from the Church Facebook page. Uploaded by Evangelist Emijowo Ogungbure

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Though Ilajeland is dominated by the Aladura movement of which the COCANO is one, other religious groups are present in the area.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Children born to parents who identify as members of the group acquire membership status of the group.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Those not born into the group also have the opportunity to become members by exercising their rights of choice of association.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: To be fully integrated into the group members are encouraged to attend the group's school of theology where doctrinal issues and other fundamental beliefs of the church are taught to enrolees. Those who attend the school of theology and complete the training become full members of the church.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 20000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: The group has a supreme leader who is the monarch and arrow head of the church. The group has branches which are led by prophets. The prophet and leader of the branch churches are supported by junior prophets and other categories of leaders.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

- ↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
 - Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

- Yes

- Notes: The leaders are believed to possess supernatural powers bestowed upon them by the supreme being.

- ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:
 - No

- ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
 - Yes

- Notes: The group believes that the closer an individual is to the supreme being, the more of the supreme being that manifests in such an individual. The leaders of the group are perceived as people who dedicate time to seeking the supreme being regularly. As such, their supernatural powers are perceived to have been bestowed upon them by the sovereign high God.

- ↳ Powers are inherited:
 - No

- ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
 - No

- ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
 - No

- ↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
 - Yes

- Notes: Prophets are assumed to occupy the highest office in the group. When an individual begins to manifest some supernatural powers and able to use divine means to cure illnesses, avert evil and crisis or neutralise other strange powers, such a person is seen as a prophet, groomed and allowed to grow in that spiritual office.

- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes

- ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: Although it is not in all cases but leaders may under some circumstances indicate their successor.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Though followers are free to express their views about the leader's actions, they are never quick to speak about the failures of their leaders.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Other leaders in the group respect and honour the monarch. They are therefore usually not quick to bring charges of failure against the supreme leader of the group.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: Political leaders do not usually interfere in the internal affairs of the group.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The religious group subscribe to the authority of the Holy Bible.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the part of the bible being read or studied, there are background stories associated with some books and chapters of the Holy Bible.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Recognised leaders of the group expound on the scriptures and teach the members from it during their group meetings.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: They carve wooden crosses and swords for spiritual warfare as well as white and red flags which symbolise peace and war respectively among other objects.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions

etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the spirit/mind and body are both distinguishable parts of the human being. While the body is the frame/vehicle that sustains the spirit, the spirit gives life to the body and enables the body move around. When the spirit departs the body, it lays lifeless. Also when the body is brutally wounded or fatally crushed, it may no longer be able to support the continuous flourishing of the spirit, hence, death occurs.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The church beliefs that there is yet another life at the expiration of this current one.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that there two distinct kinds or locations of the afterlife. One is above and is characterised by bliss and joy. It is reserved for those who obey the divine commands of the supreme being in the current life. The location of the other afterlife is beneath. It is

characterised by pain, anguish and sorrow. This one is reserved for those who live in disobedience to divine command in this current life.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that supernatural beings exist. They believe that the supreme being is at the apex of the complex structure of supernatural beings and that he has a retinue of other supernatural beings who support his government. Satan however is at the apex of the supernatural beings who antagonise God and his will. He has constantly waged wars against the supreme being and all he cares about (including humans). Satan is held to also have a retinue of supernatural beings who aid him in trying to actualise his ambitions and goals.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The group describes him as possessing human qualities and attributes. They see him as possessing mighty hands, eyes that cannot behold iniquity etc.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The monarch is seen as the manifestation of the high god just as every human. The group holds that a; humans are formed in the image of the high god.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supreme high god is full of mercy, he is forgiving and gracious.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that as the creator of the whole world, the supreme high god has knowledge of all that exists in the world.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample

region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that his eyes are upon every being and that he is watching everywhere all at the same time. He is held as one who sees in the light as well as in the dark. They say that darkness is light to him.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme being discerns the thoughts of the heart and the intent of the mind

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that every knowledge about the world is held by him since he created all that currently exists on earth..

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that he is the uncaused cause, the unmoved mover and the beginning of all events in the world. They believe that it is his will that is established on the earth.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god recompenses the actions of all human beings. He marks the actions of all and rewards them according to their deeds.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Just as he rewards all actions of all mortals, the group believes that the high god equally punishes every act of disobedience and cruelty. They believe that his eyes are too holy to behold evil. When he spots any evil, he brings judgement on the perpetrators of such acts.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: When the supreme high god is perceived not to have actively acted to bring about a course of event, he is even held remotely as the force behind the action. He is seen by the church as being the remote mover and cause of all actions.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high god is infinitely benevolent. He is all good and in him is no evil whatsoever. So it is the believe of the group that the supreme high god exhibits positive emotions always.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The negative emotions the supreme high god exhibits according to the group are always towards a good end. When he is angry, it is because his anger is kindled against injustice and evil. When he punishes a fellow, it is because he is avenging the evil such a fellow had done and for which they refuse to repent and show remorse.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high god doe hunger but not for food or other human cravings. He hungers for justice, fairness and uprightness.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supreme being exhibits all conceivable good features. He is kind, loving, compassionate, slow to anger and wrath etc

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes the supreme high god communicates with the living when prayers are offered to him.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supreme being communicates with the living through nature, the environment and through special signs and circumstances.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the spirits of humans who once lived the face of the earth are ubiquitous and present among or in the immediate surrounding of the living.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: The group holds that previously human spirits cannot be seen easily but they do not deny their presence and involvement in the world of the living. Just as the supreme being and other supernatural beings cannot be seen but their existence is affirmed by them, they also hold that those previously human spirits are present though largely invisible.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: The knowledge the human spirits possess are those restricted to the geographical area and happenings around their physical world of interaction and existence.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the human spirits have knowledge largely unrestricted within the sample region.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: Except when through extra ordinary circumstances, human spirits' knowledge is restricted only within the sample region.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that spirits of deceased humans who lived within the sample region but who have now translated this realm of existence continue to hover over the physical human community. These spirits can see everywhere normally visible in public or private.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– Yes [specify]: The group holds that having translated the human realm, the spirits now have deeper knowledge of things which humans are incapable of due to the limitations of the human nature.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
– No

Notes: The group holds that human spirits only hunger for revenge and retribution

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that human spirits could be jealous, angered, provoked etc

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that human spirit communicate with the living whenever they decide to pass vital information across to their living relations.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds the view that this is possible among those who take part in ancestor worship. The Egungun cult is a cult of the ancestors in Yorubaland where the COCANO group is largely found. Those among their kin and kith who participate in this cult engage in divination practices to the spirits of their benevolent ancestors. It is the duty of the ancestors to engage them and accept their propitiation if such is not observed in breach.

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Human spirits communicate with the living through signs, nature and environmental forces etc

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Non-human supernatural beings are just like the supreme being. They possess his character and ability. They can do as much as the supreme being bids them and so exhibit fairly every knowledge of this world as the supreme being exhibits.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that these class of beings can reward and also punish as the supreme being grants them permission to carry out such duties on his behalf.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the Non-human supernatural beings possess hunger for the execution and completion of their tasks as assigned by the supreme being.

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They are dutiful, obedient to the supreme being and highly disciplined.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that mixed human-divine beings exist but they do not specifically fear them or adore them.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: The group believes that these could be apparitions of some sort of beings whose physical presence may not be totally felt physically but can leave certain signs of their presence behind wherever they go. Strange strong breeze, chilling sensations or other feelings could be impacted on those who are within the area where they appear to be or where they engage human beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in

public):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that mixed human-divine beings know the reasons behind hidden and strange occurrences which humans do not naturally know because of their limited capacity to venture into the metaphysical realm.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world as much as the supreme being grants them leave.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: They possess hunger for retribution, vengeance and revenge for evil done by the person being targeted by the mixed human-divine being.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They are very meticulous with their ambition and goals.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Notes: This is not entirely so. Though some of the non-human supernatural beings including angels are reputed to be specialists in certain aspects of the angelic affairs/ministry, they can still be deployed to carry out general or special duties as the occasion demands. Gabriel is known to be a conveyer of good tidings and a faithful messenger, Michael is the leader of the warriors and Raphael the angel of healing. However, when situation demands, they could be involved in some other tasks.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: the group holds that supernatural beings care about sex with animals and same sex couples.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: The group makes a clear distinction between reasonable and unreasonable risks. A reasonable risk may include undertaking a cause of action which is meant to bring progress, development and other positive causes while an unreasonable risk involves risks that have no benefit to those undertaking it. It may include just deciding to jump off a cliff or failing to obey traffic rules which endanger the lives of those taking the risk and others around them at the time of such actions. The group therefore encourages members to take positive and reasonable risks but discourages the taking of unreasonable risks.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that supernatural beings care about compliance with divine instructions and obeying constituted authority.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings mete out punishment also through the activation of the law of Karma.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishments are sometimes meted out to draw erring members of the church back to the supreme being for protection and forgiveness.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious

group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the extent of punishments that can be visited on humans who flout divine instructions is simply boundless. It may include physical and mental

impairment and all forms of disability.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: The group holds that rewards in this life consists of everything good that can be conceived in the human mind. This includes attaining to desired and unexpected heights in career, family life etc.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
– Yes

Notes: The messiah's whereabouts is known but his exact time of return (coming back) is unknown.

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the messiah came to fulfil the first part of his mission in his first coming. He is coming back in this lifetime to complete the other part of his assignment; vis to take his followers with him to eternal life.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

- ↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes

- ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
- ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
- ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No
- ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
 - No
- ↳ Other survival condition:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes

- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The group also advocates cleanliness, sympathy for those in need of it etc

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Male members who are unmarried are not encouraged to be sexually active. They are also not expected to mate with animals or be involved in same sex partners.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Female members who are unmarried are not encouraged to be sexually active. They are also not expected to mate with animals or be involved in same sex partners.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 12

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 48

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The church does its best to meet the pressing needs of her members by assisting those in need of basic support for survival.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through

an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The government provides formal education to the members of the group through the establishment of schools which cater for the educational needs of the member

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with government bureaucracies in their normal line of duties

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government provides public food storage to all citizens of the country.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government attempts the provision of water management to the group's adherents but such efforts have not been successful or sustained.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Transport infrastructure is mainly provided the group's adherents through private investors.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government levies taxes on the group's adherents.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with the nation's Police structure.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's members interact with and are subject to the country's judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are subject to the decisions of the country's judicial system.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Properties of members may only be seized by a competent court of law. This would only happen when such properties so seized are found to be proceeds of crime or if they are obtained by fraudulent means.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are subject to the country's legal code

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's members may participate in the nation's institutionalised military if they so desire.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The language spoken in that part of Yorubaland is commonly accepted and used in the gathering of the group's members.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The group adopts the Gregorian calendar and uses same in planning their activities.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group relies on the food items produced by others as they visit markets around them to procure their nutritional needs.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards